

AGRIBUDDY “SANPHOK” (SOIL ANALYZER ON NITROGEN, PHOSPHORUS, AND POTASSIUM): AN INNOVATION FOR ENHANCED NUTRIENT MANAGEMENT

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AgriBuddy “SANPhoK” (Soil Analyzer on Nitrogen, Phosphorus, and Potassium): An Innovation for Enhanced Nutrient Management

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Abstract

The AgriBuddy “SANPhoK” (Soil Analyzer on Nitrogen, Phosphorus, and Potassium) device used in this study aimed to improve nutrient management in agricultural farms. This device utilizes sensors to measure essential soil nutrients—nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), and potassium (K)—providing farmers with accurate, real-time data to optimize fertilizer application. The analyzer offers a cost-effective solution for small to medium-scale farms by integrating Arduino-based technology and a user-friendly interface. This device addresses imbalanced nutrient distribution, decreasing crop yield and soil degradation. Its key components include its ability to determine the amount of nutrient in mg/kg with an indication of “Low, Moderate, or High”. In this study, the researcher experimented with three (3) trials with the same soil, assessing the precision and accuracy of the device. The results indicated that the device achieves similar and close average measurements, ensuring exactitude. T-test for dependent means was used and showed no significant difference between the pre-testing and post-testing with a p value of 0.483, proving the constant and precise ability of the product. Moreover, the product was determined to have similar nutrient level classification with the traditional Soil Test Kits (STKs) and has been more efficient than the conventional method. Farmers can make informed decisions regarding the type and amount of fertilizer needed through precise monitoring. Its real-time feedback can lead to more precise decisions, reduce environmental impacts, and ultimately contribute to more efficient farm operations.

Keywords: *Arduino Soil NPK sensor, soil nutrient management, soil sampling, imbalanced nutrient distribution*

Introduction

Soil testing is essential for sustainable agriculture, but accessing soil nutrient analysis is a significant challenge in the Philippines. Ongoing droughts and low crop yields result from inadequate soil assessments. Problems with soil quality have long been a risk for farmers but are often ignored. This has become a significant concern in agriculture. In Manolo Fortich, Bukidnon, local farming is vital, but poor soil quality creates challenges. Delays in receiving soil tests and recommendations from the Department of Agriculture can take months, making it hard to improve farming practices. This affects current harvests and future sustainability. There is an urgent need for faster support to help farmers tackle these issues. Traditional soil testing methods involve laboratory analysis, which can be time-consuming, expensive, and often inaccessible to smallholder farmers who comprise a significant portion of the country’s agricultural sector.

Bukidnon is widely known for its rich agriculture. According to PSA (2022), Bukidnon had the highest annual growth rate of value of production in agriculture. Soil testing is crucial, especially in the vicinity of the Province of Bukidnon.

As of 2024, The Department of Agriculture (DA) has yet been tasked to establish soil testing around the country as the President of the Philippines, Ferdinand Marcos Jr., addresses the lack of soil analysis in the country, which is crucial to farmers in knowing what crops are suitable on their respective lands. The country needs more awareness and education on proper soil nutrient management practices, which is evident. Many farmers need access to the information and technology required to monitor and adjust soil fertility effectively. This knowledge gap results in issues such as nutrient imbalances and over-fertilization, which lower productivity and contribute to environmental problems such as water contamination due to nutrient leaching. According to the Australian Centre for International Agricultural Research (2023), soil degradation poses a significant environmental threat facing the agricultural sector of the Philippines, with about 70% of the country's land area being affected by soil acidification, fertility decline, and erosion.

There may be existing methods of soil testing such as the Minus One Element Technique (MOET) whereby farmers grow plants using seven chemical formulations, also methods such as chemical analysis, which is performed in a soil testing laboratory or through a Soil Test Kit (STK). When a soil test kit is used, farmers can determine the level of nutrients in their soil through chemical reagents that change color upon reaction with their soil sample, however, does not reveal numerical values on the nutrient content of the soil (Sagcal, 2022).

Assessing soil quality and nutrients before farming is essential in analyzing the possible crop yield. Soil testing is a process in which the soil’s biological, chemical, and physical properties are analyzed. According to Lukowska et al. (2019), soil testing is crucial in modern agriculture to maximize productivity, safeguard the environment from excessive fertilizer use, and conserve resources such as money and energy during production. However, even though soil testing is the beginning of responsible and sustainable nutrient management, several farmers still need to learn about such services. According to O’Connell & Osmond (2022), soil testing has been widely adopted but, so far, has yet to yield the anticipated corresponding outcome.

Soil samples are collected and analyzed to determine their composition, characteristics, or nutrient levels. Soil testing mainly includes

NPK (Nitrogen, Phosphorus, and Potassium) values.

Nitrogen, among the three values, is one of the most essential. Plants require more Nitrogen than any other nutrient. Nitrogen is converted to amino acids, becoming responsible for producing necessary enzymes and structural parts of the plant (Zayed et al., 2023). Only a tiny amount of Nitrogen in the soil is available for plants because 98% of the Nitrogen in the soil is in organic forms that cannot be taken up by plants. In contrast, plants can easily absorb mineral forms of Nitrogen, including nitrate and ammonia. Soil microorganisms convert organic forms of Nitrogen to mineral forms when they decompose organic matter and fresh plant residues, which is then identified as the process of mineralization. Values of soil nitrogen can be classed into one of five descriptive categories from "Very low" to "Very High". The greater the value for soil nitrogen supply, the more likely it is that the microorganisms in the soil will convert organic Nitrogen into mineral nitrogen for plant uptake.

Phosphorus (P), Nitrogen, and potassium are nutrients that plants need in relatively large quantities for average growth. P is a structural component of deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) and ribonucleic acid (RNA) in living organisms, essential for reproduction. Plants and animals derive internal energy from phosphorus-containing compounds such as Adenine triphosphate (ATP). Insufficient phosphorus supplies in plants result in a decreased synthesis of RNA, which produces a protein, resulting in depressed growth (Khan et al., 2023). Enough amounts of phosphorus results in higher grain production, improved crop quality, greater stalk strength, increased root growth, and better crop maturity. In contrast, phosphorus-deficient plants are stunted, containing limited root systems and thin stems.

Aside from nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P), the amount of potassium (K) levels in soil is dramatically essential. According to the Potash Development Association (2019), average plant growth requires large quantities of potassium. Several functions of potassium in plants are related to physiological conditions and stress, which include efficient Nitrogen and water use, drought tolerance, frost resistance, and resistance to pests and diseases. Subsequently, when plants lack potash, they result in more robust, more vigorous crops that suffer a significant loss in challenging growing seasons.

Nitrogen (N), Phosphorus (P), and Potassium (K) values are measured in milligrams of Nitrogen per kilogram of soil (mg/kg) and are also called potentially mineralizable nutrients. For Nitrogen, the best balance is achieved by a "Moderate" soil nitrogen supply (25-50 mg-N/kg) suitable for clay soil. Values above 50mg/kg are considered "High" but, in contrast, suitable for loam soil. On the other hand, levels of Phosphorus indicate that below 30 mg/kg P requires additional phosphorus "Low"; therefore, above 30 mg/kg is considered "Moderate", and above 50 mg/kg is considered "High". Subsequently, amounts of potassium are recommended to range from 26 mg/kg as "Moderate" and above 45 mg/kg as "High".

This study addresses challenges related to the lack of soil testing in the country, which leads to improper soil nutrient management. It aims to fill that gap by exploring the potential of Arduino-based technology for real-time soil nutrient testing. An NPK sensor can detect the three essential nutrients in soil: nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium levels. This research seeks to develop an accurate and practical system for field use.

The scope of this study encompasses the development of a Soil NPK Analyzer – AgriBuddy SANPhok, designed to provide real-time nutrient readings to improve fertilizer management in agricultural farms, particularly in Tankulan, Manolo Fortich, and Bukidnon. This research specifically focuses on measuring Nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium, excluding other essential nutrients. Moreover, this device is designed for real-time data collection but does not include advanced wireless connectivity. This study hopes to anchor fertilizer recommendations to the FertRight application, designed to provide recommendations based on NPK levels outlined by the Bureau of Soil and Water Management. Furthermore, several limitations affect the device's generalizability and performance. First, environmental factors such as temperature and moisture variations could affect sensor readings, as extreme weather conditions are beyond control.

Furthermore, this research aims to benefit the following sectors: Department of Agriculture (DA), Department of Science and Technology (DOST), Department of Environmental and Natural Resources (DENR), Bureau of Soils and Water Management (BSWM), Environmental Non-Government Agencies, Division of Bukidnon, Local Government of Manolo Fortich, Cooperatives and Farmer Associations, farmers, and the environment. This study aims to enable the country to develop targeted programs and initiatives towards improving soil health, thereby enhancing agricultural productivity. Farmers, as the primary beneficiaries, can benefit from immediate access to soil nutrient data, allowing them to make informed decisions on fertilizer applications. This will eventually lead to improved crop yields, reduced costs, and better resource management.

Research Questions

Generally, this study will aim to explore the feasibility and potential of implementing a Soil Analyzer that will facilitate real-time identification and analysis of Nitrogen (N), Phosphorus (P), and Potassium (K) levels in agricultural soils, thereby enhancing nutrient management for farms. Specifically, this study will focus on answering the following questions:

1. What will be the specifications of the device?
 - 1.1. size/mass;
 - 1.2. structure; and
 - 1.3. power source?

2. What will be the performance factors of the device in terms of its:
 - 2.1. lifespan;
 - 2.2. precision; and
 - 2.3. cost?
3. Will there be a significant difference between the pre-testing and post-testing of the device?
4. What will be the difference between AgriBuddy SANPhoK and traditional Soil Test Kits (STK) in terms of:
 - 4.1. nutrient level classification; and
 - 4.2. time efficiency?

Methodology

Research Design

The research design used in this study was quasi-experimental. The effectiveness of the robot was assessed by comparing the specific outcomes before the robot was introduced (pre-test) and after its implementation (post-test). The study was divided into several phases: device development, soil sampling, pre-testing, modification, post-testing, and data analysis using a T-test.

The experiment following the assembly of the device was the pre-testing phase, which was conducted using the collected soil samples. During this phase, the device's accuracy was tested through three trials, using the same soil samples to ensure consistency. This pre-test established a baseline for comparison with later results. After modifications, the soil testing was subjected to the post-testing phase, where the soil samples were tested again under the same conditions, and three trials were conducted.

The results from the post-test were compared to the pre-test results to determine if the modification led to significant improvements in the device's performance. In validating the findings, a T-test was employed to statistically analyze whether there was a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test. This further allowed the reliability and effectiveness of the Soil NPK Analyzer to be objectively evaluated, ensuring the improvements were statistically significant—this experimental design, exploring pre-test and post-test values, aimed to assess the device's capabilities thoroughly.

Instrument

These are the following materials used in this study:

Arduino Nano Board, JXCT NPK Sensor (Power DC 9V, Measuring Range 0-1999mg/kg), 16x2 LCD, MAX485 Modbus Module, 9-12 DC Power Supply (Power Bank Jump Starter JX27), Jumper Wires (8.1 cm, 14.3 cm), Breadboard, and USB Cable, Toggle Switch.

Arduino Nano Board

The Arduino Nano Board is a compact microcontroller version of Arduino based on the ATmega328P chip. It serves as the brain of the project, providing a platform for programming and connecting the sensors and modules.

NPK Sensor

The JXCT Soil NPK sensor used in this study provides a quick responsive, high precision and portable sensor that works with Modbus RS485. Unlike traditional detection methods, this sensor gives real-time measurement when you insert its probe in soil and get the reading using Arduino. It can measure from 0-1999mg/kg (ml/l). It is responsible for measuring the NPK values found in the soil tested.

16x2 Liquid Crystal Display (LCD) I2C

The 16x2 Liquid Crystal Display (LCD) I2C is a visual output that can display 16 characters across 2 lines. This is where the NPK values are displayed.

MAX485 Modbus Module

This serves as the relay module of the project. MAX485 to RS485 interface module allows the use of RS485 differential signaling for long-distance communications up to 1200 meters. It allows communication between the Arduino and sensors; it allows Arduino to send and receive data from the NPK sensor.

Power Supply

The power supply used in this project is the Jump Starter JX27 power bank. It refers to the battery that supplies necessary voltage and current to power the Arduino board and its connections. It matches the required voltage needed by the device to power.

Jumper Wires (F-M Dupont Cable, M-M Dupont Cable)

These wires enable the connection between the different components in the breadboard or between the microcontroller and a component. Female-to-male (F-M) and male-to-male (M-M) Dupont cables are both used to connect the components.

Breadboard

In this study, the role of the breadboard is to provide a flexible, organized space for connecting all the electrical components. It allows the connection between the components such as the Arduino nano, MAX485 module, NPK sensor, and other wires to create the entire system.

USB Cable

The USB cable has two main purposes: power supply and data transfer. It provides power to the Arduino from the computer or the power bank, allowing the circuit to function. It also allows the code upload from the computer to the Arduino and facilitates communication.

Toggle Switch

A toggle switch is an electrical switch that can be in one of the two positions: on or off. Once the lever is pulled, it facilitates that power on or power off of the device.

Procedure

The data gathering process for developing the Real-time Soil NPK Analyzer began by collecting and purchasing the necessary materials such as the Arduino Nano Board, MAX485 Modbus Module, NPK Sensor, 16x2 LCD, breadboard, and connecting wires. After the purchase, the materials were tested.

The wiring of the required components was then facilitated. Components such as the MAX485 Modbus Module and Arduino Nano were directly connected to the breadboard. The power needed for the circuit was connected to the positive pins, and the board received power from the power bank via a USB cable.

For the connection between the Arduino Nano and the Modbus module, the R0 and DI pins of the Modbus were connected to the D2 and D3 pins of the Arduino using software serial communication. The DE and RE pins of the Modbus were connected to the D7 and D8 pins of the Arduino. Regarding the NPK sensor, the four wires in the sensor were identified. The brown wire (Positive) 12-24V was connected through combined female cables, which were then attached to the cheerful pin slot in the breadboard. The black wire (Negative) 12-24V was connected through combined female cables to the ground pin on the breadboard. The sensor's blue wire (485-B) was connected to the B pin of the Modbus module, and the yellow wire (485-A) was connected to the A pin of the module.

A 16x2 LCD was used to display the values from the NPK sensor. The VCC was connected to the 5V slot, and the GND pin was connected to the negative ground pin. The SDA and SCL pins of the 16x2 LCD were connected to the A4 and A5 pins on the Arduino Nano, respectively. With these connections made, the device was enabled to display NPK values with corresponding identification as "Low," "Moderate," or "High."

After assembling and integrating all components, comprehensive testing of the Soil NPK Analyzer device was conducted to verify that the sensor was working efficiently in terms of measurement (mg/kg) and its ability to display the level of measurement. The evaluation was conducted in a controlled environment to ensure consistency and reliability of results. Consistent soil samples were used for both pre-and post-test trials, ensuring that the nutrient content in the soil remained constant throughout the experiment, thus preventing variability that could affect the results. While exact conditions such as temperature or humidity were not varied in the study, the soil testing process was conducted under consistent settings, with no significant external factors, including rain or extreme heat, affecting the soil samples during the trials.

By maintaining the same soil samples and ensuring controlled testing conditions, the study aimed to isolate the performance of the NPK Analyzer as the primary variable. This allowed the device's precision and effectiveness to be measured accurately without external influences affecting the results.

Table 1. *Optimum Values of NPK (mg/kg)*

<i>Nutrient</i>	<i>Optimum Levels (ppm or mg/kg)</i>
Nitrogen (N)	25-50 mg/kg
Phosphorus (P)	30-50 mg/kg
Potassium (K)	26-45 mg/kg

Table 2. *Values of NPK (mg/kg) with Corresponding Nutrient Level Classification*

<i>Nutrient</i>	<i>LOW (mg/kg)</i>	<i>MODERATE (mg/kg)</i>	<i>HIGH (mg/kg)</i>
Nitrogen	<25 mg/kg	>25 mg/kg	>50 mg/kg
Phosphorus	<30 mg/kg	>30 mg/kg	>50 mg/kg
Potassium	<26 mg/kg	>26 mg/kg	>45.05 mg/kg

According to Soil Organization Australia (n.d.), the best nitrogen balance was achieved by a moderate soil nitrogen supply (25-50mg/kg), which was suitable for clay soil. On the other hand, according to PennState Extension (2017), recommended levels of

Phosphorus ranged between 30 to 50 ppm (or 30mg/kg to 50mg/kg). Below 30mg/kg of Phosphorus was considered "Low," above 30mg/kg was considered "Moderate," and above 50mg/kg was considered "High."

Subsequently, recommended amounts of Potassium for vegetables ranged between 26 and 45mg/kg, 16 and 25mg/kg for grass and other plants, 100 and 120mg/kg for sands, and 181 and 240mg/kg for other soils (Potash Development Association, 2019). Levels below 26mg/kg were classified as "Low," above 26mg/kg were classified as "Moderate," and above 45mg/kg were considered "High."

Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to ethical standards by ensuring that all components and processes involved were safe for the researcher and, most ultimately, the environment. The soil samples were collected from a private lot with proper permission from the owners. No harm was caused during the conduct of this study, as it was ensured that the testing involved non-invasive measurements of soil nutrients. Additionally, the research was conducted transparently, with proper acknowledgements given to all contributors and sources through in-text citations and adequate recognition in the References section following the APA 7th edition format. All safety protocols were followed, and proper disposal of waste materials was ensured to minimize environmental impact

Results and Discussion

In this section, data collected from the device's pre-testing and post-testing will be presented and analyzed. The results will be shown through graphic representation of tables and will also be validated with statistical analysis through a T-test. With this chapter, the researcher aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the AgriBuddy SANPhoK performance.

Problem 1. What are the specifications of the device?

Size/Mass

Table 3. *Size/Mass Pre-Test*

<i>Device</i>			
<i>Material</i>	<i>Mass</i>	<i>Measurement</i>	
Soil NPK Analyzer Electrical Components	700g	Height: 150mm	Width: 75mm
Sintra Board Frame and Structure	350g	Height: 230mm	Width: 140mm

Table 4. *Size/Mass Post-Test*

<i>Device</i>			
<i>Material</i>	<i>Mass</i>	<i>Measurement</i>	
Soil NPK Analyzer Electrical Components	700g	Height: 150mm	Width: 75mm
Marine Board	1000g	Height: 230mm	Width: 140mm

The table presents the mass of the device and its structure. It illustrates the primary construction materials of the Soil NPK Analyzer, the overall mass of the electrical components (breadboard, Arduino Nano, 16x2 LCD, MAX485 Modbus Module, Power Bank, Toggle Switch), and its frame. According to Cope Plastics (n.d.), Sintra boards are lightweight yet durable, dent and scratch-resistant. It is a chemical and heat-resistant PVC board suitable for holding electrical components. However, compared with the Marine Board, also known as marine-grade plywood, the marine board is extreme and more durable. The material is resistant to deformation and breaking due to its multi-layer structure (Pico Plywood, 2024). Moreover, the marine board is designed to resist moisture and water exposure, making it ideal for housing electrical components. It also has good thermal stability and quality that can easily be drilled, cut, and customized.

Structure

Table 5. *Structure*

<i>Sintra Board Structure (Pre-Test)</i>	
Length	240mm
Width	140mm
Height	230mm
Total Area:	32,200mm ²
<i>Marine Board Structure (Post-Test)</i>	
Length	240mm
Width	150mm
Height	250mm
Total Area:	37,500mm ²

This table indicates the specific information about the device's length, width, and height necessary to the foundation of this project. The structural integrity of the marine board is better than that of the Sintra board. According to Pico Plywood (2024), marine board

exhibits greater structural strength, capacity to support heavy loads, and better load distribution, which holds electrical components mounted without bending the frame.

Power Source

Table 6. Power Source

Pre-Test	
Powered by Laptop	Approximately 2.5 – 3 Hours
Post Test	
Powered by Power Bank	Approximately 30 days (when used 20 minutes/day)

Table 6 indicates the power sources used in the study’s pre-and post-test and shows the difference between the durations the power source can employ. According to Anker Support (n.d.), Anker power banks can last up to 300-500 complete charge cycles, and when used 20 minutes per day, they are estimated they are estimated to last up to 30 days. On the other hand, an average laptop consumer is around 15 mA to 30 mA under light load; using the Soil Analyzer can last approximately three hours.

Problem 2. What are the performance factors of the device?

Lifespan

Table 7. Lifespan

Pre-Test	
Power Bank	3.5 years
Sintra Board	10 years
Post Test	
Power Bank	3.5 years
Marine Board	15 – 25 years

Table 7 illustrates the device's performance factor with its materials: Sintra board compared with marine board. According to Anker Philippines (n.d.), a good-quality power bank is expected to last between 1.5 and 3.5 years of usage. Sintra boards are reported to last for 10 years under light conditions (PrintMoz, 2024). On the other hand, marine-grade plywood is known to last 15-25 years, particularly when coated with a protective finish (Taylor, 2024).

Precision

Table 8. Precision Pre-Test

Trial No. (40seconds)	Nitrogen (mg/kg)	Nutrient Level (N)	Phosphorus (mg/kg)	Nutrient Level (P)	Potassium (mg/kg)	Nutrient Level (K)
1	22 mg/kg	<25 Low	30 mg/kg	>30 Moderate	20 mg/kg	<26 LOW
2	24 mg/kg	<25 Low	30 mg/kg	>30 Moderate	20 mg/kg	<26 LOW
3	24 mg/kg	<25 Low	30 mg/kg	>30 Moderate	20 mg/kg	<26 LOW
Average	23.33 mg/kg	Low	30 mg/kg	Moderate	20 mg/kg	Low

Table 8 displays the values generated for Nitrogen (N), Phosphorus (P), and Potassium (K) in three trials with the same soil, each with a duration of 40 seconds. The precision and accuracy of the NPK sensor are illustrated. The soil NPK sensor measures a range from 0-1999 mg/kg and reveals a ±2%F. S precision, meaning the margin of error is 2% of the sensor’s maximum capacity. For example, if the sensor reads 50 mg/kg, the actual value could be between 48 mg/kg and 52 mg/kg (JXCT, 2024).

Table 9. Precision Post-Test

Trial No. (60 seconds)	Nitrogen (mg/kg)	Nutrient Level (N)	Phosphorus (mg/kg)	Nutrient Level (P)	Potassium (mg/kg)	Nutrient Level (K)
1	24 mg/kg	<25 Low	30 mg/kg	>30 Moderate	20 mg/kg	<26 LOW
2	24 mg/kg	<25 Low	30 mg/kg	>30 Moderate	20 mg/kg	<26 LOW
3	24 mg/kg	<25 Low	30 mg/kg	>30 Moderate	20 mg/kg	<26 LOW
Average	24 mg/kg	Low	30 mg/kg	Moderate	20 mg/kg	Low

Table 9 displays the values generated for Nitrogen (N), Phosphorus (P), and Potassium (K) in three trials with the same soil, each lasting 60 seconds. This illustrates the precision and accuracy of the NPK sensor. For Nitrogen, the best balance is achieved by a “Moderate” soil nitrogen supply (25-50 mg-N/kg), suitable for clay soil. Values above 50 mg/kg are considered “High” but are more suitable for loam soil (Soil et al. Australia, n.d.). For Phosphorus, recommended levels range between 30 and 50 ppm (or 30 mg/kg and

50 mg/kg) (PennState Extension, 2017). Soil phosphorus levels below 30 mg/kg are considered “Low,” levels above 30 mg/kg are considered “Moderate,” and levels above 50 mg/kg are considered “High.”

Subsequently, recommended amounts of potassium for vegetables are indicated as 26-45 mg/kg, 16-25 mg/kg for grass and other plants, 100-120 mg/kg for sands, and 181-240 mg/kg for other soils (Potash Development Association, 2019). Based on these recommendations, levels below 26 mg/kg are classified as “Low,” levels above 26 mg/kg are classified as “Moderate,” and levels above 45 mg/kg are considered “High.”

Cost

Table 10. Cost Analysis

Soil NPK Analyzer			
Specifications	Quantity	Unit Price	Amount
Arduino Nano Board	1	P199.00	P199.00
JXCT NPK Sensor	1	P1,779.00	P1,779.00
16x2 LCD	1	P149.00	P149.00
MAX485 Modbus Module	1	P49.00	P49.00
F-M Dupont Cable	1 Pack	P49.00	P49.00
M-M Dupont Cable	1 Pack	P49.00	P49.00
Breadboard	1	P35.00	P35.00
Electrical Tape	1	P30.00	P30.00
Toggle Switch	1	P110.00	P110.00
Device Frame			
Marine Board (Recycled)	1	P200.00	P200.00
Nails	1 Pack	P20.00	P20.00
Overall Estimated Cost:		P2, 669.00	

This cost analysis table shows the itemized components and its corresponding costs along with its quantity, unit price, and estimated amount.

Problem 3. Is there a significant difference between the Pre-testing and the post-testing of the device?

Table 11. T-Testing

Paired Samples T-Test	Pre-Test (mg/kg)	Post-Test (mg/kg)	Mean Difference	t-statistics	p-value	Conclusion
Nitrogen (N)						
Trial 1	22 mg/kg	24 mg/kg	-0.67	-1.00	0.423	No significant difference
Trial 2	24 mg/kg	24 mg/kg				
Trial 3	24 mg/kg	24 mg/kg				
Phosphorus (P)						
Trial 1	30 mg/kg	30 mg/kg	0	N/A	N/A	Constant Data
Trial 2	30 mg/kg	30 mg/kg				
Trial 3	30 mg/kg	30 mg/kg				
Potassium (K)						
Trial 1	20 mg/kg	20 mg/kg	0	N/A	N/A	Constant Data
Trial 2	20 mg/kg	20 mg/kg				
Trial 3	20 mg/kg	20 mg/kg				

This t-test table summarizes the statistical comparison between the pre-test and post-test nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium measurements in the same soil.

No significant difference is observed between the pre-test and post-test nitrogen levels, with a mean difference of -0.67 mg/kg, a t-statistic of 1.00, and a p-value of 0.432, more significant than 0.05. This suggests that the changes in nitrogen levels are likely attributable to the ±2%F.S. sensor precision, where the margin of error is 2% of the sensor’s maximum capacity, as explained by JXCT (2024). For phosphorus and potassium, the values remain constant across trials, indicating no statistical variation.

Problem 4. What is the difference between the use of the AgriBuddy SANPhoK and the traditional Soil Test Kits (STK) in terms of;

Nutrient Level Classification

Table 12. Nutrient Level Classification

	SANPhoK	Soil Test Kit (STK)
Nitrogen (N)	Low	Low
Phosphorus (P)	Moderate	Moderate
Potassium (K)	Low	Low

This table shows the nutrient level classifications provided by the SANPhoK and the traditional Soil Test Kits (STK). It is determined that there is no difference between the results of the two methods.

According to Sagcal (2022), STKs determine the nutrient levels in the soil through chemical reagents that change color upon reaction with the soil sample. However, this method does not provide the numerical values of the nutrient content.

Time Efficiency

Table 13. *Time Efficiency*

	<i>SANPhoK</i>	<i>Soil Test Kit (STK)</i>
Waiting Time	60 seconds	11 days

This table indicates the waiting time for the results when the SANPhoK and the Soil Test Kit are used. According to the University of Minnesota (n.d.), processing the soil samples usually takes 7-10 business days. Moreover, this timeframe may be exceeded due to pending soil testing accommodated within the municipality. The soil sample was sent in this study on October 31, 2024, and the results arrived on November 11, 2024.

Limitations on the Research Design and Material

This study primarily focused on developing and testing a Soil NPK (Nitrogen, Phosphorus, Potassium) Analyzer designed to provide real-time nutrient readings to improve fertilizer management in agricultural farms, particularly in Tankulan, Manolo Fortich, and Bukidnon. The scope of the research included the design and assembly of the device using Arduino technology, an NPK sensor, and an LCD Display. The study covered the processes of coding, pre-testing, structure development, and post-testing to ensure the accuracy and precision of nutrient readings in mg/kg. The device was tested under controlled conditions with soil samples from the target location to assess its functionality, efficiency, and potential to enhance sustainable farming practices.

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Furthermore, several limitations affected the device's generalizability and performance. First, environmental factors such as temperature and moisture variations were found to potentially affect sensor readings, as extreme weather conditions were beyond control. Moreover, the research did not cover soil nutrient testing for all soil types or conditions outside Tankulan, Manolo Fortich. Lastly, financial and technical constraints limited the study from incorporating additional features, such as wireless data transmission or mobile application integration, which could have enhanced the user experience.

Conclusions

The development of a real-time soil analyzer, AgriBuddy SANPhoK, using Arduino technology, has proved precise and accurate. The findings suggest that using the NPK sensor ensures consistency and is comprehensive through the nutrient level classification, which is critical for scaling challenges with finding appropriate fertilizers.

Based on the gathered results of this study, the following recommendations are made:

Expand calibration to varying soil types and conditions to enhance applicability to wider range of agricultural environments.

Incorporate additional nutrient sensors such as soil pH, providing more comprehensive understanding of soil health.

Explore wireless connectivity such as integrating it into a mobile application that displays the nutrient levels and recommends appropriate fertilizers.

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